

Preparation and Characterisation of Nickel(II) and Chromium(III) Complexes with *N*-Acylamino Acids and their Adducts

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Complexes of the type NiL_nXH_2O , adducts of the type $NiL_nB_nXH_2O$, $Cr_2(III)L_nOH_nXH_2O$ and $Cr_2(III)L_nXH_2O$ ($LH=N$ -formyl, *N*-acetyl, monochloroacetyl, trifluoroacetyl-*L*-phenylalanine, *N*-benzoyl, monochloroacetyl, trichloroacetyl, trifluoroacetyl-*DL*-alanine, *N*-benzoylglycine and *N*-benzoyl-*L*-leucine; $B=imidazole$, 2-methylimidazole and 1,2-dimethylimidazole; $n=2$; and $X=0-6$) have been prepared and characterised with the help of various physical and spectroscopic techniques. The molar conductance values of nickel(II) adducts are in the range for two ion electrolytes while chromium(III) complexes are non-electrolytes in methanol. Electronic absorption spectra and magnetic moment values show an octahedral geometry for nickel(II) and chromium(III) complexes. The coordination of carboxylate group to metal ion is bidentate as indicated by the ir spectra. The isotropic value of g in chromium(III) complexes indicate an octahedral geometry and polymeric nature.

INFRARED absorption spectra have been studied for nickel(II) complexes with amino acids like glycine¹, *DL*-valine², *DL*-leucine³ and *DL*-phenylalanine⁴. It is found that two molecules of amino acids coordinate to nickel(II) ion through N(amino) and O(carboxyl) in a trans planar arrangement while other coordination sites are occupied by carboxyl oxygen of neighbouring ligands or water molecules to complete the octahedral configuration. The nickel(II) complexes with *N*-acetyl glycine⁵, *N*-benzoylglycine⁶, *N*-acetyl-*DL*-valine⁶, *N*-acetyltryptophane⁷, *N*-acetyl-*DL*-alanine⁸, *N*-acetyl-*DL*-leucine⁹ and their amine adducts have been reported. All the complexes are of the type NiL_nXH_2O and $NiL_nB_nYH_2O$ ($L=N$ -acetyl- or *N*-benzoylamino acid anion; $B=Py$, 3-pic, 4-pic, pipz, *o*-phen; $X=2-6$; $Y=0-2$; and $n=1-2$). Magnetic moments and electronic spectra are consistent with hexacoordinated nickel(II) with some distortion from the octahedral symmetry which suggests the presence of MO_6 and MO_4N_2 chromophores for the hydrate and base adducts. Infrared spectra agree with the coordination of the amino acids from the carboxyl group.

Chromium(III) forms 1:3 (metal-ligand) green as well as purple complexes with glycine, alanine, valine and leucine. The coordination through carboxylate and amino group is revealed by the infrared spectra of the complexes. Infrared spectral data also reveal the presence of coordinated water molecules. In all the cases, the solid state reflectance spectra showed two absorption bands around 17 000 and 23 000 cm^{-1} corresponding to the transition ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) (ν_1) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2) respectively¹⁰.

The aim of the present study has been to evaluate the effects of substituent on the amino

group, reduces the ligand field of the in-plane donor atoms, diminishes the affinity of the amino group for the metal ions and could permit a variety of coordination types.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R grade. All the *N*-acylamino acids prepared in the laboratory (their purity checked by tlc) were characterised by m.p. determination and ¹H nmr spectra. The following *N*-acylamino acids were prepared: *N*-formyl-*L*-phenylalanine (For PheH), *N*-benzoyl-*DL*-alanine (Bz-AlaH), *N*-benzoylglycine (Bz-GlyH), *N*-benzoyl-*L*-leucine (Bz-LeuH), monochloroacetyl-*DL*-alanine (MCA-AlaH), trichloroacetyl-*DL*-alanine (TCA-AlaH), trifluoroacetyl-*DL*-alanine (TFA-AlaH), *N*-acetyl-*L*-phenylalanine (Ac-PheH), monochloroacetyl-*L*-phenylalanine (MCA-PheH) and trifluoroacetyl-*L*-phenylalanine (TFA-PheH). The following amines were used: imidazole (Im), 2-methylimidazole (2MeIm) and 1,2-dimethylimidazole (1,2-DimeIm).

The amino acids like *L*-phenylalanine, *DL*-alanine, *L*-leucine, imidazole, 2-methylimidazole and 1,2-dimethylimidazole (all Sisco), nickel nitrate, methanol, glycine, lead nitrate, EDTA (disodium salt), nitric acid, hydrochloric acid and sulphuric acid (all AnalaR), trichloroacetic acid, chloroacetic acid, acetic anhydride, acetic acid, formic acid, benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate and benzoyl chloride (all E. Merck) and trifluoroacetic acid (Ferax) were used. The solvents were purified and dried by known method¹¹. All other reagents used as such.

Synthetic procedure: Trifluoroacetic anhydride¹², chloroacetyl chloride and trichloroacetyl chloride¹³, *N*-formylamino acid¹⁴, *N*-acetylamino acid^{15,16},

N-benzoylamino acids^{17,18}, monochloroacetyl and trichloroacetyl amino acids¹⁹ and trifluoroacetyl amino acids²⁰ were prepared by the known methods. Sodium salts of the *N*-acylamino acids were prepared²¹ and characterised by infrared spectra.

Bis(N-acylamino-carboxylato)nickel(II) hydrates (NiL₂XH₂O): Freshly prepared nickel(II) hydroxide (~ 0.001 mol) was added to a hot solution of the *N*-protected amino acid (0.002 mol) in methanol (50 ml) solvent. The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for ~ 4 h. The unreacted nickel(II) hydroxide was removed by filtration. The resulting light green solution was evaporated on a water-bath to a semi-solid mass which was dried in a desiccator (sulphuric acid) for a few days and then under reduced pressure.

Bis(amine)bis(N-acylamino-carboxylato)nickel(II) hydrates (NiL₂B_nXH₂O) (L = amino acid anion, B = imidazole, 2-methylimidazole and 1,2-dimethylimidazole, n = 2 and X = 0-2): The amine (~ 0.002 mol) was added to a solution of NiL₂XH₂O (0.001 mol) in methanol (50 ml). The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for ~ 3 h. The solution was then filtered and evaporated on a water-bath to a semi solid mass. The resulting adduct was washed twice with diethyl ether to remove any excess of the amine. The semi-solid residue was dried in a desiccator (sulphuric acid) for a few days and then powdered and dried under reduced pressure.

Tetra(N-acylamino-carboxylato)-μ-dihydroxodichromium(III) hydrates: A mixture of hexa-aquo chromium(III) chloride (0.02 mol) and *N*-acylamino acid (0.04 mol) dissolved in ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 0.5 h. After adding sodium hydroxide (0.06 mol) it was again refluxed for 6-7 h. The solution was filtered hot and evaporated on a water-bath to a semi-solid mass which was washed with hot water, placed in a sulphuric acid desiccator and then powdered and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes with monochloroacetyl, trichloroacetyl and trifluoroacetyl-DL-alanine were prepared from chromium(III) nitrate nonahydrate in a similar manner.

Hexa(N-acylamino-carboxylato)dichromium(III) hydrates: A mixture of hexa-aquo chromium(III) chloride (0.02 mol) and the *N*-protected amino acids (0.062 mol) dissolved in ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 0.5 h. Rest of the procedure followed was the same as given in the bis-type complexes.

Physical measurements: The magnetic susceptibility of the nickel(II) and chromium(III) complexes at room temperature was measured by Gouy method²² using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as a calibrant²³. Molar conductance (millimolar solutions in methanol) was measured on a Toshniwal CIOI/02A conductivity bridge using a conventional dip type platinum electrode²⁴. The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP3-300 spectrophotometer in the range 4000-200 cm⁻¹, the electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectro-

photometer, the esr spectra at room temperature on a Jeol FE-3XG X-band instrument (0-5000 gauss). Elemental analysis data were obtained from the Regional Sophisticated and Instrumentation Centre, Chandigarh. The metal ions were estimated volumetrically using EDTA. M.p.s. were determined in capillaries using a liquid paraffin-bath in a thiel's tube and are uncorrected.

Results and Discussion

Forty complexes of nickel(II) and fourteen complexes of chromium(III) in 1:2 and 1:3 (metal-ligand ratio) with *N*-formyl, *N*-acetyl, monochloroacetyl, trifluoroacetyl-L-phenylalanine, *N*-benzoyl-glycine, *N*-benzoyl-L-leucine, monochloroacetyl, trichloroacetyl and trifluoroacetyl-DL-alanine, and nickel(II) adducts with amine like imidazole, 2-methylimidazole and 1,2-dimethylimidazole have been prepared and characterised with the help of various physical and spectroscopic techniques (Table 1). All the complexes are stable in air except two nickel adducts of 1,2-dimethylimidazole with trifluoroacetyl-DL-alanine and trifluoroacetyl-L-phenylalanine and two chromium(III) complexes with MCA-AlaH and TFA-AlaH in the molar ratio of 1:3 which are highly hygroscopic in air. These complexes are green to greyish except the complexes with For-PheH which are light purple. All the complexes are soluble in polar solvents and insoluble in non-polar solvents. The molar conductance of the nickel(II) adducts is comparable to two ion electrolytes while chromium(III) complexes are non-electrolytes in methanol. The magnetic moment values of the nickel(II) complexes lie in the range 2.89-3.39 B.M. which is normal for high-spin octahedral or slightly distorted octahedral complexes. The magnetic moment values of the chromium(III) complexes are somewhat lower (3.09-4.32 B.M.) than the spin-only value (3.87 B.M.), except complexes sl. no. 49 (Table 1). This may be due to partial spin-pairing via bridging groups indicating the dimeric nature of these complexes.

In the ir spectra (Table 2) the NH stretching vibration of the *N*-acylamino acids absorbs in the range 3270-3370 cm⁻¹, while in the nickel(II) and chromium(III) complexes it absorbs at 3280-3420 and 3260-3400 cm⁻¹ respectively due to different types of hydrogen bonding. The NH bending mode, also called amide-II band occurs at 1515-1557 cm⁻¹ in the *N*-acylamino acids. In the nickel(II) and chromium(III) complexes this band occurs at the same or slightly lower position (1510-1560 cm⁻¹) indicating the non-coordinating behaviour of the amide nitrogen. Amide-I band of the *N*-acylamino acids falls in the range 1595-1635 cm⁻¹. Except in trifluoroacetyl- and trichloroacetyl amino acids, it rises upto 1685-1700 cm⁻¹ due to electron-withdrawing inductive effect of three halogen atoms attached to the adjacent carbon atom. In the nickel(II) and chromium(III) complexes, the amide-I band shifted to slightly lower or higher frequency due to hydrogen bonding.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES AND THEIR ADDUCTS

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				λ_M Ω cm ⁻¹	μ_{eff} mol ⁻¹ B.M.
				C	N	H	Metal		
1.	Ni(For-Phe) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Light green	215-16	49.15 (50.10)	5.58 (5.84)	4.95 (5.01)	11.90 (12.31)	65	3.31 (291)
2.	Ni(Bz-Ala) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Green	210-11	49.06 (50.10)	4.90 (5.84)	4.97 (5.01)	12.20 (12.31)	61	3.18 (291)
3.	Ni(Bz-Gly) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Green	231-33	46.93 (47.89)	5.89 (6.20)	3.85 (4.43)	12.70 (13.08)	64	3.14 (290)
4.	Ni(Bz-Leu) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Green	160-62	56.96 (55.22)	3.96 (4.95)	6.11 (6.37)	10.10 (10.47)	54	3.33 (290)
5.	Ni(For-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	Green	105-07	52.91 (52.89)	13.97 (14.50)	4.97 (4.83)	10.20 (10.18)	71	2.89 (313)
6.	Ni(Bz-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂	Green	100-04	52.44 (53.88)	14.00 (14.50)	4.58 (4.83)	10.00 (10.18)	64	3.39 (313)
7.	Ni(Bz-Gly) ₂ (Im) ₂ .H ₂ O	Green	97-9	51.92 (50.61)	14.84 (14.76)	4.20 (4.56)	10.40 (10.86)	59	2.89 (313)
8.	Ni(Bz-Leu) ₂ (Im) ₂ .H ₂ O	Green	93-100	56.49 (56.38)	11.88 (12.33)	5.98 (6.16)	8.37 (8.66)	78	3.15 (312)
9.	Ni(For-Phe) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	Green	95-7	54.97 (53.76)	12.88 (13.44)	5.63 (5.44)	9.30 (9.44)	79	2.96 (313)
10.	Ni(Bz-Ala) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂	Green	100-03	54.76 (55.35)	12.94 (13.34)	5.39 (5.27)	9.70 (9.71)	70	2.98 (313)
11.	Ni(Bz-Gly) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	Green	85-7	52.96 (52.26)	13.78 (14.07)	4.92 (5.02)	9.57 (9.88)	69	3.15 (313)
12.	Ni(Bz-Leu) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	Sea green	100-04	58.47 (57.54)	11.07 (11.84)	6.29 (6.48)	8.05 (8.32)	90	3.06 (311)
13.	Ni(For-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	Green	77-80	55.51 (56.69)	12.79 (13.22)	5.85 (5.66)	9.00 (9.29)	45	2.95 (313)
14.	Ni(Bz-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	Sea green	78-81	55.97 (56.69)	12.66 (13.22)	5.93 (5.66)	9.20 (9.29)	71	3.20 (313)
15.	Ni(Bz-Gly) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	Deep green	81-4	54.79 (55.35)	12.91 (13.33)	5.57 (5.27)	9.80 (9.75)	64	3.26 (307)
16.	Ni(Bz-Leu) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	Green	80-3	59.93 (58.61)	10.60 (11.39)	7.07 (6.78)	7.80 (8.00)	81	3.25 (311)
17.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Sea green	180-83	51.60 (52.07)	4.99 (5.52)	5.22 (5.52)	11.80 (11.63)	52	3.16 (308)
18.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Whitish green	108-10	45.47 (45.83)	4.51 (4.86)	4.39 (4.51)	9.90 (10.24)	64	2.96 (308)
19.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Sea green	115-20	43.13 (42.93)	3.95 (4.55)	3.27 (3.57)	9.50 (9.59)	76	3.22 (308)
20.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Light green	77-80	30.10 (28.30)	6.62 (6.60)	4.10 (4.24)	13.70 (13.90)	81	3.20 (308)
21.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Sea green	212-15	21.59 (21.85)	4.42 (4.98)	2.18 (2.49)	10.80 (10.49)	63	3.16 (308)
22.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Light green	112-14	26.87 (25.91)	6.02 (6.04)	2.81 (3.02)	12.70 (12.70)	77	3.35 (308)
23.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	Greenish	97-8	54.60 (55.35)	13.32 (13.83)	5.05 (5.27)	9.60 (9.71)	78	3.10 (309)
24.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	Green	89-90	49.68 (49.70)	11.66 (12.42)	4.59 (4.43)	8.70 (8.72)	90	3.16 (309)
25.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	Bluish	85-7	45.16 (46.99)	11.05 (11.74)	3.79 (3.63)	8.60 (8.25)	117	3.20 (309)
26.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂ .H ₂ O	Green	90-1	36.73 (35.42)	17.14 (15.49)	5.12 (4.42)	10.70 (10.88)	150	2.90 (308)
27.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂	Greenish	100-05	29.23 (29.00)	13.59 (12.68)	3.07 (2.71)	9.30 (8.91)	82	3.33 (311)
28.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂ .H ₂ O	Bluish white	60-3	34.91 (33.04)	15.02 (14.45)	4.03 (3.44)	9.93 (10.15)	93	3.14 (311)
29.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂	Parrot green	90-2	56.93 (56.69)	12.66 (13.22)	5.51 (5.66)	9.30 (9.29)	60	3.15 (311)
30.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	Light green	73-5	49.35 (49.86)	11.39 (11.63)	5.00 (4.98)	7.86 (8.17)	135	2.95 (311)
31.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂	Green	70-2	49.67 (48.45)	11.17 (11.30)	4.53 (4.03)	8.00 (7.94)	102	3.17 (309)
32.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	Parrot green	76-9	39.32 (37.89)	13.93 (14.73)	4.86 (4.91)	9.99 (10.35)	162	3.17 (312)
33.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	Green	75-7	29.73 (30.50)	10.87 (11.86)	3.45 (3.38)	8.55 (8.33)	118	3.08 (312)
34.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂	Green	72-3	35.03 (36.54)	14.70 (14.21)	3.97 (3.72)	9.98 (9.98)	145	3.12 (310)
35.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	Green	70-2	58.03 (57.91)	12.05 (12.66)	5.85 (6.03)	8.30 (8.89)	88	3.13 (312)
36.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	Light green	67-70	51.82 (52.45)	10.93 (11.47)	5.34 (5.19)	8.20 (8.06)	151	3.04 (311)

(Table 1 contd.)

37.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Bottle green	53-4	—	—	—	6.97 (6.31)	141	—
38.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Deep green	75-8	39.88 (38.98)	13.72 (13.68)	5.84 (5.91)	9.60 (9.57)	198	3.12 (3.11)
39.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	Light green	87-9	92.66 (93.42)	11.09 (11.69)	3.74 (3.62)	8.20 (8.21)	68	3.31 (3.12)
40.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ ·H ₂ O	Dark green	—	—	—	—	9.50 (9.26)	115	—
41.	[Cr(For-Phe) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Violet	195-39	51.14 (50.95)	4.95 (5.99)	4.84 (4.88)	11.16 (11.04)	44	3.44 (289)
42.	[Cr(Bz-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Greyish	165-68	49.02 (50.95)	5.65 (5.99)	4.44 (4.88)	11.30 (11.04)	16	3.31 (289)
43.	[Cr(Bz-Gly) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Greyish	160-62	48.50 (48.75)	5.99 (6.32)	3.91 (3.61)	12.20 (11.73)	18	3.28 (289)
44.	[Cr(Bz-Leu) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Greyish	135-36	57.54 (56.21)	4.66 (5.04)	6.24 (5.76)	9.50 (9.36)	12	3.20 (289)
45.	[Cr(MCA-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Dirty green	118-20	30.45 (38.84)	6.80 (6.93)	4.23 (4.08)	11.90 (12.50)	33	3.53 (309)
46.	[Cr(TCA-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Greyish	120-22	20.85 (20.97)	3.59 (4.89)	2.72 (2.62)	8.60 (9.09)	21	3.57 (309)
47.	[Cr(TFA-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·H ₂ O	Greyish	122-24	27.89 (26.37)	6.82 (6.15)	2.78 (2.85)	11.20 (11.42)	38	3.47 (309)
48.	[Cr(For-Phe) ₂] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Violet	120-23	55.15 (55.72)	5.14 (6.50)	4.86 (4.95)	8.50 (8.04)	26	3.77 (289)
49.	[Cr(Bz-Ala) ₂] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Greyish	140-43	55.21 (55.72)	4.99 (6.50)	4.94 (4.95)	8.55 (8.04)	32	4.02 (289)
50.	[Cr(Bz-Gly) ₂] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Dirty green	100-02	52.87 (53.64)	6.04 (6.95)	3.81 (4.30)	9.00 (8.60)	31	3.76 (289)
51.	[Cr(Bz-Leu) ₂] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Greyish	85-7	60.23 (60.62)	5.33 (5.44)	5.99 (6.47)	7.10 (6.73)	25	3.09 (294)
52.	[Cr(MCA-Ala) ₂] ₂ ·6H ₂ O	Bottle green	100-03	33.31 (32.99)	7.97 (7.69)	4.82 (3.84)	8.60 (8.67)	50	—
53.	[Cr(TCA-Ala) ₂] ₂ ·6H ₂ O	Greyish	98-100	21.04 (22.31)	4.67 (5.20)	2.15 (3.60)	6.30 (6.44)	39	3.61 (309)
54.	[Cr(TFA-Ala) ₂] ₂ ·6H ₂ O	Bottle green	101-03	29.39 (29.80)	7.32 (6.95)	2.99 (2.48)	7.30 (7.90)	53	—

TABLE 2—RELEVANT IR BANDS* (cm⁻¹) OF N-ACYLAMINO ACIDS, SODIUM SALTS AND NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES AND ADDUCTS

Sl. no.	Compd.	ν_{NH}	δ_{NH}	ν_{CO} (ket)	ν_{CO} (asym)	ν_{CO} (sym)	$\Delta\nu^{**}$
1.	(a) For-PheH	3 360vs	1 515s	1 595vs	1 710vs	1 210s	500
	(b) For-PheNa	3 470s	1 515s	1 660vs	1 582	1 398	184
	Ni(For-Phe) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 315s	—	—	—	—	—
2.	(a) Bz-AlaH	3 370vs	1 540s	1 620vs	1 720s	1 210s	510
	(b) Bz-AlaNa	3 440s	1 525vs	1 630vs	1 570vs	1 405s	165
	Ni(Bz-Ala) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 340s	—	—	—	—	—
		3 400bs	1 540sh	1 630s	1 595s	1 410s	185
3.	(a) Bz-GlyH	3 340vs	1 540vs	1 595vs	1 740vs	1 180vs	560
	(b) Bz-GlyNa	3 325s	1 530sh	1 638vs	1 570s	1 395s	175
	Ni(Bz-Gly) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 245s	—	1 590s	1 570s	1 400s	170
		3 320s	—	—	—	—	—
4.	(a) Bz-LeuH	3 330s	1 520s	1 635s	1 725vs	1 225s	500
	(b) Bz-LeuNa	3 350s	1 522s	1 623vs	1 575vs	1 412s	163
	Ni(Bz-Leu) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 400bs	—	1 590bs	1 570vs	1 400s	170
		—	—	—	—	—	—
5.	(a) Ac-PheH	3 335vs	1 540bs	1 620s	1 695vs	1 240s	455
	(b) Ac-PheNa	3 280vs	1 545s	1 635s	1 570vs	1 405s	165
	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 280vs	1 540w	—	1 620vs	1 410	210
6.	(a) MCA-PheH	3 320vs	1 540s	1 630vs	1 700vs	1 250s	450
	(b) MCA-PheNa	3 320bs	1 530m	1 660s	1 595s	1 395m	200
	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 400s	1 530mb	1 660sh	1 630sb	1 410s	220
		—	—	—	—	—	—
7.	(a) TFA-PheH	3 300vs	1 555vs	1 630mb	1 700vs	1 180m	520
	(b) TFA-PheNa	3 440bs	1 535s	1 665s	1 600vs	1 405s	195
	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 420bs	—	1 700s	1 605vs	1 420s	185
8.	(a) MCA-AlaH	3 380vs	1 545s	1 620vs	1 720vs	1 210s	510
	(b) MCA-AlaNa	3 340bs	1 550s	1 660s	1 595s	1 402s	193
	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 390bs	1 540sh	1 660sh	1 620vs	1 410s	210
		—	—	—	—	—	—
9.	(a) TCA-AlaH	3 310s	1 515s	1 685s	1 700s	1 230vs	470
	(b) TCA-AlaNa	3 360vs	1 495s	1 695vs	1 605vs	1 400s	205
	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 380bs	1 500s	1 690vs	1 610vs	1 410s	200

(Table 2 contd.)

10.	(a) TFA-AlaH	3 270s	1 557s	1 700s	1 720vs	1 190b	530
	(b) TFA-AlaNa	3 370bs	1 530sh	1 705vs	1 605vs	1 405s	200
	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 380bs	—	1 700vs	1 160	1 420s	190
11.	Ni(For-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	3 380sh 3 260bs	1 540sh	1 655s	1 600vs	1 395s	205
12.	Ni(For-Phe) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂ ·H ₂ O	3 360s 3 250sb	1 520sh	1 650s	1 590vs	1 385s	205
13.	Ni(For-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	3 380sb	1 535sh	1 650s	1 590vs	1 390s	200
14.	Ni(Bz-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂	3 370sb	1 530s	1 630s	1 590s	1 395m	195
15.	Ni(Bz-Ala) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂	3 380s 3 200sb	1 520m	1 635s	1 615s	1 410s	205
16.	Ni(Bz-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	3 400s	1 530sh	1 630s	1 595s	1 400vs	195
17.	Ni(Bz-Gly) ₂ (Im) ₂ ·H ₂ O	3 310s	1 530s	1 630s	1 590s	1 385s	205
18.	Ni(Bz-Gly) ₂ (2Me) ₂ ·H ₂ O	3 400sh 3 360bs	1 540m	1 635s	1 600s	1 395s	195
19.	Ni(Bz-Gly) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	3 370bs	1 530s	1 625s	1 600s	1 405s	195
20.	Ni(Bz-Leu) ₂ (Im) ₂ ·H ₂ O	3 360sb	1 530s	1 630s	1 595s	1 400vs	195
21.	Ni(Bz-Leu) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂ ·H ₂ O	3 400s 3 200bs	1 540sh	1 635s	1 600sb	1 405s	195
22.	Ni(Bz-Leu) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ ·H ₂ O	3 400sb	1 540sh	1 635s	1 600m	1 405vs	195
23.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	3 265s	1 540sh	1 630sh	1 590vs	1 400s	190
24.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂	3 400s	—	1 640sb	1 600sb	1 405s	195
25.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	3 400s	1 540sh	1 640sb	1 605m	1 410s	195
26.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	3 400s	1 525s	1 740s	1 640vs	1 410s	230
27.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂ ·H ₂ O	3 400s	1 520sh	1 740vs	1 630vs	1 410s	220
28.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	3 400s 3 450	1 510s	1 740s	1 625s	1 405s	220
29.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	3 350sb	1 520m	1 710sh	1 610s	1 415s	195
30.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂	3 360s	1 545sh	1 720sh	1 620s	1 425s	195
31.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ ·H ₂ O	—	—	—	—	—	—
32.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂ ·H ₂ O	3 380sb	1 540sh	1 740s	1 640s	1 410s	230
33.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂ ·H ₂ O	3 400sb	1 530sh	1 745m	1 640s	1 420s	220
34.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 380sb	1 520m	1 740s	1 630s	1 415s	215
35.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂	3 370sb	—	1 690s	1 600s	1 410s	190
36.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂ ·H ₂ O	3 360sb	—	1 700vs	1 630s	1 410s	210
37.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	3 370vs	1 545sh	1 710vs	1 620s	1 410vs	210
38.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂ ·H ₂ O	3 400sh 3 340	1 540sh	1 720s	1 590s	1 410s	180
39.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂	3 340sb	1 545sh	1 715vs	1 620sh	1 415vs	205
40.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ ·H ₂ O	—	—	—	—	—	—
41.	[Cr(For-Phe) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 300bs 3 380bs	1 520w	1 650w	1 610s	1 422s	188
42.	[Cr(Bz-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 400bs 3 330m	1 550vs	1 620s	1 595w	1 412s	183
43.	[Cr(Bz-Gly) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 260bs	1 535s	1 635vs	1 570m	1 410s	160
44.	[Cr(Bz-Leu) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 320bs 3 420bs	1 540s	1 625vs	1 595m	1 420s	175
45.	[Cr(MCA-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 300bs	1 530m	1 655w	1 620s	1 430s	200
46.	[Cr(TCA-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·4H ₂ O	3 400bs	1 510s	1 700vs	1 630vs	1 430s	200
47.	[Cr(TFA-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 300bs	1 530s	1 710vs	1 640vs	1 432s	208
48.	[Cr(For-Phe) ₂] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 310bs 3 280bs	1 530w	1 665m	1 605s	1 430s	175
49.	[Cr(Bz-Ala) ₂] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 320bs 3 420m	1 540m	1 640s	1 605w	1 430s	175
50.	[Cr(Bz-Gly) ₂] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 280bs	1 525s	1 630vs	1 570m	1 415m	155
51.	[Cr(Bz-Leu) ₂] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3 320bs	1 540m	1 640bs	1 605m	1 430s	175
52.	[Cr(MCA-Ala) ₂] ₂ ·6H ₂ O	3 320bs	1 520w	1 665w	1 620w	1 430w	190
53.	[Cr(TCA-Ala) ₂] ₂ ·6H ₂ O	3 320bs	1 510s	1 695vs	1 630vs	1 430s	200
54.	[Cr(TFA-Ala) ₂] ₂ ·6H ₂ O	3 320bs	1 550m	1 715bs	1 650vs	1 438s	212

*bs=broad and strong, vs=very strong, w=weak, m=medium, s=strong, sh=shoulder. **Δν=ν_{OCO} (asym), ν_{OCO} (sym).

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (IN METHANOL, cm^{-1}) OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES AND THEIR ADDUCTS

Sl. no.	Compd.	$(\nu_2) {}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (P)$	$(\nu_2) {}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (F)^*$	
1.	Ni(For-Phe) ₂ .2H ₂ O	25 300	15 000	13 600
2.	Ni(For-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	26 200	15 600	13 400
3.	Ni(For-Phe) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	26 000	15 400	13 400
4.	Ni(For-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	26 300	14 900	13 400
5.	Ni(Bz-Ala) ₂ .2H ₂ O	25 000	14 900	13 700
6.	Ni(Bz-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂	26 000	15 600	13 400
7.	Ni(Bz-Ala) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂	25 800	15 000	13 300
8.	Ni(Bz-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	25 000	14 900	13 400
9.	Ni(Bz-Gly) ₂ .2H ₂ O	25 600	14 900	13 600
10.	Ni(Bz-Gly) ₂ (Im) ₂ .H ₂ O	26 000	15 600	13 400
11.	Ni(Bz-Gly) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	25 800	15 000	13 800
12.	Ni(Bz-Gly) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	25 300	14 900	13 500
13.	Ni(Bz-Leu) ₂ .2H ₂ O	25 100	15 000	13 600
14.	Ni(Bz-Leu) ₂ (Im) ₂ .H ₂ O	26 000	15 500	13 400
15.	Ni(Bz-Leu) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	25 100	15 000	13 300
16.	Ni(Bz-Leu) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	25 100	14 800	13 400
17.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ .2H ₂ O	25 100	15 200	13 600
18.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	26 000	15 500	13 500
19.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂	25 100	15 000	13 800
20.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	25 400	14 900	13 500
21.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ .2H ₂ O	25 300	15 000	13 600
22.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	25 800	15 000	13 400
23.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	25 400	15 000	13 400
24.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	25 400	14 900	13 600
25.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ .2H ₂ O	25 600	15 200	13 500
26.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	26 700	15 900	13 400
27.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂	25 600	15 800	13 800
28.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ .2H ₂ O	—	15 200	13 500
29.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ .2H ₂ O	25 400	15 000	13 600
30.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂ .H ₂ O	26 700	15 600	13 500
31.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	25 500	15 800	—
32.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ .2H ₂ O	26 000	15 300	13 500
33.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ .2H ₂ O	25 800	15 100	13 700
34.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂	26 100	15 500	13 400
35.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	25 600	15 200	13 400
36.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	25 600	15 000	13 500
37.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ .2H ₂ O	25 800	15 300	13 600
38.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂ .H ₂ O	26 700	16 300	13 400
39.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂	26 000	15 500	13 500
40.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	26 000	15 400	13 500

*Due to low symmetry or close lying triplet-single transition.

TABLE 4—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (cm^{-1}) AND g VALUES OF CHROMIUM(III) COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P)$	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (F)$	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$	B	g
1.	[Cr(For-Phe) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	33 672	24 100	18 000	533	2.050
2.	[Cr(Bz-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	32 812	23 600	17 400	600	2.020
3.	[Cr(Bz-Gly) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	32 580	23 500	17 200	613	2.032
4.	[Cr(Bz-Leu) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	32 812	23 600	17 400	600	2.026
5.	[Cr(MCA-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	32 562	23 400	17 300	588	2.053
6.	[Cr(TCA-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	32 725	23 500	17 400	588	2.053
7.	[Cr(TFA-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	32 682	23 600	17 200	597	2.038
8.	[Cr(For-Phe) ₂] ₂ .2H ₂ O	32 758	24 200	18 000	595	2.038
9.	[Cr(Bz-Ala) ₂] ₂ .2H ₂ O	32 689	23 400	17 400	576	2.044
10.	[Cr(Bz-Gly) ₂] ₂ .2H ₂ O	31 990	22 900	17 100	554	2.020
11.	[Cr(Bz-Leu) ₂] ₂ .2H ₂ O	32 154	23 000	17 200	554	2.002
12.	[Cr(MCA-Ala) ₂] ₂ .6H ₂ O	32 154	23 000	17 200	554	2.029
13.	[Cr(TCA-Ala) ₂] ₂ .6H ₂ O	31 754	22 700	17 000	544	2.035
14.	[Cr(TFA-Ala) ₂] ₂ .6H ₂ O	31 811	22 700	17 100	539	2.032

Three criteria i.e. (i) $\Delta\nu$ difference between symmetric and asymmetric carboxylate stretching frequencies²⁴⁻²⁶; (ii) direction of band shift (DBS)²⁷ and (iii) position of $\nu_{\text{OCO}} \text{sym}^{28}$ are known in order to decide the coordination behaviour of carboxylate group. Since all the

complexes are hydrated, the position of the symmetric carboxylate stretching vibration, which is due to the band directly connected with the oxygen linked to metal ion can only be used to decide the nature of carboxylate binding. On the basis of these criteria, the carboxylate group coordinates as a

bridging bidentate in the nickel(II) and chromium(III) complexes. Coordination of amines through tertiary nitrogen is supported by the shift or disappearance of ir bands in adducts with respect to the same band in the free amines.

The electronic spectra of the nickel(II) complexes (Table 3) reveal two absorption bands at 14 800–16 300 and 25 000–26 700 cm^{-1} corresponding to transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3) respectively. Similarly, in the chromium(III) complexes, two bands at 17 000–18 000 and 22 700–24 200 cm^{-1} correspond to transitions ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) (ν_1) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) (ν_2) respectively. The isotropic values of g in the esr spectra of the chromium(III) complexes indicates an octahedral geometry for these complexes (Table 4).

Conclusion: An octahedral structure for the nickel(II) complexes is proposed with coordination

- 1
 R = H.CO.CH.OH, C₆H₅, C₆H₅.CO.NH.CH.OH,
 C₆H₅.CO.NH.CH.OH, CH(CH₃)₂, CH₂.CO.NH.CH.OH, C₆H₅,
 CH₂.Cl.CO.NH.CH.OH, C₆H₅, OF₃.CO.NH.CH.OH, C₆H₅,
 CH₂.Cl.CO.NH.CH.OH, OCl₂.CO.NH.CH.OH,
 OF₃.CO.NH.CH.OH,
 B = H₂O, imidazole, 2-methylimidazole, 1,2-dimethylimidazole.

- 2
 R = H.CO.NH.CH.OH, C₆H₅, C₆H₅.CO.NH.CH.OH,
 C₆H₅.CO.NH.CH₂-, C₆H₅.CO.NH.CH.OH, CH(OH)₂,
 CH₂.Cl.CO.NH.CH.OH, COCl₂.CO.NH.CH.OH,
 OF₃.CO.NH.CH.OH,
 X = OH (Sl.nos. 41-47), OOCR (Sl. nos. 48-54, Table 1).

from four oxygen atoms of two carboxylate group and two oxygen atoms of water molecules in hydrate complexes or from oxygen atoms of two carboxylate group and two nitrogen atoms of amines in adducts (1). From the magnetic moment values and isotropic value of g, an octahedral structure is proposed for all the chromium(III) complexes with coordination from four oxygen atoms of two carboxylate groups and two oxygen atoms of bridging hydroxyl groups (in 1 : 2 ratio) or two oxygen atoms of bridging carboxylate groups (in 1 : 3 ratio) (2). The carboxylate group coordinates to the metal ion in a bidentate manner.

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